

Hands-on-Data: Artificial intelligence for the design of public policy in Latin America

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Abstract

Although data produced by governments are abundant, in developing countries data-informed public policy design and implementation is often more an aspiration than a reality. The Hands-on-Data (HoD) initiative is a successful practical experience that gathers several stakeholders (e.g., public servants, academia- and industry-based data scientists, and a multilateral financing institution) to prototype data science products addressing specific public sector needs in Latin American countries. The first edition of HoD took place in Argentina during the last quarter of 2018, and resulted in five prototypes that used artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to address narrowly defined public policy problems. Most importantly, HoD Argentina succeeded at organizing a seven-week task force consisting of public officials and data scientists, who extracted actionable knowledge from large datasets (e.g., administrative records) while ensuring anonymity and confidentiality of sensitive information. The policy domains analyzed in HoD Argentina were: work and labor, health, education, urban public transport, and accessibility in large cities. The short but intensive interaction between the public sector and data scientists sparked the interest of key stakeholders, and resulted in new co-creation initiatives that exceed the time frame of HoD. In this way, HoD acted as a stepping stone for new data collaborations. We discuss the relevant aspects behind the organization of this initiative, and we include summarized presentations of the five data science products that resulted from the first HoD.

¹ In particular, regarding data security and ownership, privacy, and ethics of data use.

² In developing countries, an additional barrier is that public policy emergencies tend to overshadow long-term priorities, which impede many motivated and able public officers to learn and implement state-of-the-art data analysis tools.

Keywords – Artificial intelligence; Data science; Evidence-based policy making; Latin America.

1 Introduction

Like in the rest of the world, in Latin America, there is currently a wealth of data collected by the public sector. Although the use of these data can be of great help for policy design and implementation (Athey, 2017), data- or evidence-based policy making is still incipient in many countries (Höchtel et al., 2016). In the developing world, there are several barriers for this, a key one being the lack of specialized resources inside the public sector. In most Latin American countries is not only difficult to find specialized data scientists working as civil servants, but it is almost impossible to get the right combination of data governance schemes¹ and infrastructure that would otherwise be needed to produce relevant data analysis aimed at informing public policy (Rodriguez et al., 2017).² Even though, in most Latin American countries there is a vast supply of academic and industry data scientists working in the cutting edge applied AI³, they often face several limitations to interact with the public sector. Such limitations include unresolved security and confidentiality concerns, the high opportunity cost of data scientists' time, and the differences in working styles and languages between the many different professional profiles required by a data science project for public policy matters.

³ The Global Skills Index 2019, produced by Coursera (<https://www.coursera.org/gsi>), ranks Argentina in the first place in the world in the technology domain, and it also ranks very highly this country and other Latin American countries (e.g., Chile and Colombia), in all the domains considered in the global index (business, technology, and data science).

To tackle some of these barriers, CAF-Development Bank of Latin America⁴ created the project Hands-on-Data (HoD). The first edition of HoD took place in Argentina and it was coordinated by CAF and Fundación Sadosky⁵ (a public-private non-governmental organization with a long history in promoting information technology for the public good), and sponsored by a public national agency focused on monitoring and evaluating social policies in Argentina (SIEMPRO)⁶. The main objective of HoD is to catalyze, in a brief period of time (about seven weeks), functional proofs of concept addressing specific needs in several Latin American public agencies. More specifically, the first HoD aimed at facilitating the prototype of five data science products addressing specific needs of five Argentinean public sector units. This goal was reached by assembling teams of experts in the domain of interest, such as public officials with experience in data analysis, with professional data scientists (coming from both industry and academia), as well as helping in the communication and coordination of all participants along the whole production process.

2 Timeline and logistics of HoD

Simply put, the HoD initiative consists of five key stages, spanning a period of about four months:

1. identification of policy problems (four weeks);
2. match-making or team formation, that is, pairing policy problems, and corresponding civil servants, with data scientists (four weeks);
3. one-day workshop to polish the initial questions and prospective proposals;
4. writing of proposals for the development of prototypes (two weeks);
5. seven-week work to develop the prototypes.

For the first edition of HoD (in Argentina), the research department at CAF, advised by an academic econometrician and statistician, who also has vast experience in multidisciplinary work, started planning activities in July 2018. A short period after that, Fundación Sadosky and SIEMPRO joined these efforts. FS did so with its Data Science Program team and, together with SIEMPRO, worked at identifying candidate policy problems, shaping them, and contacting suitable data scientists and civil servants who could join HoD. Additionally, SIEMPRO helped in securing the access to valuable data to tackle such problems. CAF provided the financial support needed for the whole HoD initiative. Since the coordination of this project required strong ties with the public sector as well as

with the academia and industry, the participation of all organizers was crucial in all stages.

The teams succeed at identifying five policy problems to be addressed and at consolidating the data needed to answer them. Throughout seven weeks, each team created and prototyped solutions leveraged by state-of-the-art computer science techniques, ranging from ML (e.g., natural language processing, gradient boosting, Bayesian methods, deep learning) to combinatorial optimization (i.e., combinatorial data structures and algorithms in the flavor of shortest path search).

3 Projects developed in the first edition of HoD

There is no a typical HoD project, since each one was unique in terms of the type of data used (ranging from administrative social security records to real time GPS information, and electronic health records), the methodological approach to data modelling, and the conformation of teams. However, it is classify the five prototypes in two groups: projects addressing social policy problems and projects related to urban policy problems. The following subsections briefly discuss the five prototypes resulting from the first edition of HoD (HoD Argentina), starting with those dealing with social matters and concluding with those dealing with urban problems.

3.1 Scoring firms that violate labor regulations

In Latin America, about 50% of workers are not covered by contributory social security, that is, they are informal or unregistered workers (either salaried or self-employed) (CAF, 2018). In Argentina, a third of formally registered companies have at least one unregistered worker. Labor inspections are implemented by the national government (Ministry of Labor) to enforce the formal registry of all workers. However, labor inspections and there is room for increasing their effectiveness by improving the targeting of inspected companies.

Aim of the project: to build a scoring model to improve the detection of firms that avoid formally registering workers and paying the corresponding payroll taxes. This prototype sought to refine an existing predictive logistic regression (LR) model by using random forest (RF), gradient boosting machines (XGBoost), support vector machines (SVM), and other ML tools adequate for supervised prediction. All the code developed in this project is open source and almost entirely written in Python. This product was specific for the

⁴ CAF - Development Bank of Latin America. About CAF. <https://www.caf.com/en/about-caf/>. Last accessed: May 2019

⁵ Fundación Sadosky. Presentación institucional. <http://www.fundacionsadosky.org.ar/presentacion-institucional/>. Last accessed: May 2019.

⁶ SIEMPRO - Sistema de Información, Evaluación y Monitoreo de Programas Sociales. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/politicassociales/siempro>. Last accessed: May 2019.

Ministry of Labor internal functioning and is expected to inform the allocation of resources in inspection activities aimed at the enforcement of current labor regulations.

Team: the lead data scientist in this project was a PhD in Physics with vast experience in developing scoring algorithms in financial markets. The team at the Ministry of Labor consisted of senior data and policy analysts with extensive domain knowledge and with high skills for econometric analysis of employer-employee datasets.

Data: employer-employee matched datasets constructed from social security administrative records and characterizing firms along several dimensions (e.g., region, size, mean wages, economic sector, and tenure of workers), and administrative data coming from labor inspections to about 100,000 establishments, indicating whether these employers were found to have at least one unregistered worker in the year 2017. All datasets were anonymized and secured according to the usual protocol followed at the Ministry of Labor for this type of collaborations.

Methods and results: starting from the existing LR model, the lead data scientist proposed not only to innovate in terms of methods (introducing ML techniques), but also to expand the set of features included in the initial model. The feature engineering tasks required an intensive use of domain knowledge, which was assured by the collaborative work with the team at the Ministry of Labor. As a result, a set of new relevant features was included in the analysis (e.g., several metrics of firms dynamics, a broader set of employees' characteristics, the history of firms' labor inspections, and precise geospatial indicators). Regarding the methods, many alternative models were considered (e.g., RF, XGBoost, several versions of SVM and neural networks). Most of them produced noticeable improvements over the benchmark (i.e., the initial LR model). For instance, the new models produced considerable gains in the detection of firms infringing policy most often and severely. These gains were due to both the methods introduced to capture relevant underlying non-linearities in the data-generating model and to the inclusion of the new set of features. The Ministry of Labor is currently testing alternative ways of implementing the prototyped scoring in the process of labor inspections.

3.2 Detection of health phenotypes from electronic health records

Many high-incidence health conditions remain undetected for public health authorities until it is too late to intervene with prevention policies. This is typically the case of most chronic, non-communicable health conditions, but this also applies to some health problems related to sexual and reproductive health. Detecting and quantifying these health conditions (also known as, health phenotypes) are key inputs for the design of evidence-based public health policies.

Aim of the project: to develop algorithms that help the Ministry of Health in the city of Buenos Aires to detect specific health phenotypes using natural language processing (NLP) of electronic health records with unstructured text.

Team: This project had two lead data scientists. One of them is a physician specialized in statistical analysis applied to public health and the other one is an economist trained in NLP. The team at the agency in charge of generating health electronic records for the city of Buenos Aires consisted of a group of physicians with vast experience in data analysis.

Data: carefully anonymized electronic health records, including a random subset (4,400 registries) that was manually labeled (with or without the sought phenotype).

Methods and results: The project tested alternative models, ranging from naïve Bayes (NB) and gradient boosting machine (GBM) to several deep learning (DL) techniques. The best results were attained with the GBM and the poorest with NB. One health phenotype of interest was successfully identified with high precision and recall and is currently in use to measure the impact of several policy decisions related to this health problem. The prototype developed also left a standard data workflow that will be used at the agency to detect new relevant phenotypes.

3.3 Scoring the risk of high school dropout

In Latin America school dropout is a widespread problem, as only two thirds of students complete the secondary education level, and in some countries this fraction falls to less than 50% (CAF, 2016). Although the causes of this problem are multiple, identifying which schools or classrooms have more students at high risk of dropping out can be of great help to target more effective preventive interventions. The identification of this risk has been studied extensively for developed countries (Lakkaraju et al., 2015; Aulck et al. 2016; Hlosta et al. 2017), however for developing countries the lack of suitable (administrative) data, among other constraints, conditions the extent to which this type of analysis can be undertaken. One exception is Adelman et al. (2018), for the case of Guatemala and Honduras, which builds a predictive model using administrative datasets similar to those used in the HoD project that we describe below.

Aim of the project: To construct a scoring model for the risk of high-school dropout among vulnerable students in the Province of Buenos Aires (Argentina).

Team: The lead data scientist in this project is a PhD in Physics, with a strong research background in cognitive development and neuroscience. The team at the Ministry to Education comprises several backgrounds (e.g., Economics, Education, Sociology, Psychology, and Social Work).

Data: The project consolidated several (anonymized) data sources, including sociodemographic characteristics of students and their families, as well as schools' characteristics and academic results obtained (at the grade level) in the national standardized assessment test. All

datasets were anonymized and secured in the *enclave* that the Ministry of Labor provides for these type of data collaborations.

Methods and results: The team prototyped several predictive and explicative models of school dropout using alternative methods (LR, boosting, and neural networks). The individual-level (students) data contained relatively few features, which conditioned the performance of all models in terms of recall rates. Currently, the team of data scientists continues working together with the Ministry's team curating and adding new relevant features at the students' level, such as those coming from administrative datasets of the national social protection system. These datasets will introduce new sources of variation within grades and schools, allowing to better understand the role of individual characteristics in the risk of school dropout.

3.4 Detecting non-compliance of public buses' routes and timetables

Existing asymmetries in the access to public transportation reinforce other sources of inequality and contribute to increase social exclusion. Such asymmetries are present throughout the world but are pervasive in most Latin American cities (CAF, 2017). Cordoba is the Argentinean city covering the largest administrative surface (24km²) in the country, which makes the well-functioning of public transportation vital for the workings of the city.

Aim of the project: To generate a prototype tool that could help the Secretary of Transport in the city of Córdoba to monitor possible non-compliance (contract breaches) by concessionaires regarding routes and timetables of buses. The information generated by this tool is crucial to evaluate the equity in the access to public transport, since deviations from agreed routes/frequencies are more common in the poorest neighborhoods of the city. **Data:** Real-time bus tracking (GPS) data (over 600 buses reporting their position every 20 seconds).

Methods and results: To detect and quantify bus deviations the team assigned a real-time geo-labeled correspondence between actual and contracted routes using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW). Based on such correspondence, a score that quantifies the seriousness of route deviations was computed. To make the identification of invalid routes more efficient the city was partitioned in a grid, which enabled the description of a given route as a sequence of the grid's cells. The novelty introduced by the grid usage opened new possibilities to exploit the information of routes and actual timetables, for example: to detect the busiest cells; to design and implement an early warning system to detect abrupt reductions in the number of active cells; to combine data on trips with a socioeconomic characterization of households

and recommend possible re-design of bus routes and frequencies. Finally, to detect deviations from pre-established timetables, the team implemented a system of computationally efficient queries to the database to identify the number of buses actually riding in each possible time interval. This monitoring tool was developed and successfully integrated into the existing information system that manages public transport in the city of Cordoba and it will soon become fully open, thus enabling its implementation by other city governments in the country facing similar problems in their public transport systems.

3.5 An offline calculator of accessibility metrics

Urban sprawl, socioeconomic segregation, and the impacts of investments in infrastructure and transport networks are relevant issues in urban areas. These problems are influenced by geographic accessibility, that is, the possibility that people can easily transit, through the use of existing infrastructure, to destinations of their own interest (CAF, 2017). In the last decade, there has been a focus on generating metrics to both quantify and qualify accessibility to destinations such as schools, health centers, and central business districts (Brömmelstroet et al., 2014). Some of these destinations are highly concentrated in large urban areas, implying patterns of spatial dispersion that interact in non-trivial ways with city dynamics. Obtaining robust metrics of accessibility is a crucial step towards a better understanding of such dynamics, which, at the same time, is needed to improve the design, implementation, and monitoring of urban public policies.

Aim of the project: To build a prototype for a tool capable of providing information about geographic accessibility in Argentina. The aim was that the tool was a transparent, free, offline, and adaptable product so its use could be adopted by units outside the Ministry of Labor. The tool will calculate distances and travel times between (large sets of) specific origins and destinations, using different modes of transport (on foot, by car, and by public urban buses), based only in offline and open data (Open Street Map, OSM). In this context, origins are thought to represent household residences, while destinations can be economic opportunities (firm location) or service providers (schools, hospitals, etc.). A key objective of this tool was to overcome the problems associated to computing accessibility measures (e.g., travel time and/or distances between locations) from online paid services⁷, such as Google Maps, which act as important barriers in the process of public policy implementation.

Team: The lead data scientist of this project is a mathematician and PhD in Informatics Engineering, while the team at the Ministry of Labor included diverse

⁷ These services function as black boxes and do not allow users to modify their content (e.g., adding information on

streets or addresses), they have limitations when searching for large amounts of data and they depend on internet connection to perform any kind of query.

professional backgrounds (e.g., Economics, Physics, and Biology).

Data: The tool used primarily data from OSM. To compute accessibility measures by bus, we use open datasets from the City of Buenos Aires, which contain information on bus routes and time schedules in GTFS (General Transit Feed Specification) format. For most of use cases we used several other sources of open data containing geolocation of public providers (schools, health and citizen security public providers, etc.).⁸

Methods and results: Based on the input data, the tool determines, from each origin, which is the closest (according to travel time or distance) destination, for several modes of transport (e.g., by foot, car, public transportation). Since calculating the minimum path from all origins to all destinations is computationally inefficient (i.e., the algorithmic complexity is at least proportional to the size of the street graph), a main technical contribution in this context was to optimize the implementation for finding minimum paths. Last, the tool uses exclusively open data and is open source. To compute distances and travel times by car and on foot, the tool uses Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM). The prototype also implements an approach based on k-nearest neighbors (k-NN) and quaternary trees. In Lang et al. (2019) there is a summary of some use cases that were developed applying this calculator for the city of Buenos Aires. Three examples are shown in Figures 1 (distances to health provider facilities, by car), 2 (schools, by bus), and 3 (policy stations, on foot). The tool is currently being applied by the Ministry of Labor to compute metrics of accessibility to economic opportunities (using geolocalized employer-employee administrative data), while SIEMPRO is applying the tool to identify constraints in the accessibility to public services (mainly education and health) by vulnerable and young population subgroups.

Figure 1: Health providers – Quintiles of travel time (in seconds) by car. Source: Lang et al. (2019).

Figure 2: Public schools – Quintiles of travel time (in seconds) by public transportation. Source: Lang et al. (2019).

Figure 3: Policy stations – Quintiles of travel time (in seconds) on foot. Source: Lang et al. (2019).

4 Conclusion and future directions

HoD was a highly successful experience aimed at catalyzing the collaboration of professionals with widely different languages, backgrounds, motivations and cultures. In a very short period, all these heterogeneous teams were able to generate concrete data science products for the public good.

The successful experience of HoD is of special interest for countries where basic public sector provisions are absent (or are of low quality) and need rapid and inexpensive strategies to develop policy solutions or enforce and better existing policies. A key insight that arises from the HoD experience is that a truly multidisciplinary environment that facilitates the interplay between the complexity of technical issues in modern data analysis with concerns about the functioning of the public sector can lead to rapid and effective developments of data solutions to inform public policy.

⁸ The dataset containing the complete set of health public providers was built by Antonio Vázquez Brust, Tomás

Olego and Germán Rosati, from Fundación Bunge y Born, by integrating different sources of official open data.

Among all the policy issues analyzed in the first HoD, those involving urban matters were particularly attractive for all parties involved. Arguably, this is likely to obey to data readiness, which was a key characteristic in both projects dealing with urban issues. On the other hand, both data readiness as well as ethical aspects in the use of data were more difficult to address in the projects related to education, health, and labor issues. This conclusion is in line with the observed recent progress in applying AI and ML techniques to solve urban policy problems in many developing regions (Glaeser et al., 2018). Given the success of this first HoD, it is currently being replicated in other Latin American countries.

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